

The CO₂NE sampler.

Filling the cone with CO₂.

Scooping the arthropods on the water surface.

Arthropod density in three lowland rice varieties determined by FARMCOP and CO₂NE insect samplers,^a IIRRI, 1984.

Sampler	Arthropods (no./5 hills on indicated variety)											
	Brown planthopper <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>			Green leafhopper <i>Nephotettix</i> spp.			Green mirid bug <i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>			Wolf spider <i>Lycosa pseudo-annulata</i>		
	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36
FARMCOP	7.2 a	4.0 a	1.6 a	44 a	2.8 a	13.6 a	17.6 a	12.2 a	8.4 a	9.2 a	6.4 a	5.2 a
CO ₂ NE	5.2 a	4.8 a	3.2 a	21 b	4.4 a	15.6 a	22.8 a	17.2 a	13.6 a	9.2 a	8.4 a	7.6 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to t-test (P < 0.01).

The CO₂ NE sampler is inexpensive and easy to handle. A tank containing 22.5 kg of CO₂ costs about \$10 and is enough to sample 2,000 or more hills. In the field, a portable tank with 300 ml of CO₂, can be used to sample 30 to 40

hills.

In a field trial comparing the CO₂NE and a formerly used FARMCOP suction machine, there was almost no difference in the number of arthropods collected (see table).¹

Brown shield bug attack on rice

P.B. Chatterjee, entomologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Rice Research Station, P. O. Chinsurah R. S., Hooghly, India

A pentatomid or shield bug damaged rice in Dinajpur District, West Bengal, in 1983. Dinajpur is between 25.2° and 26.5°N and 88° and 89° E. Wet season lowland rice is the principal crop, but summer and pre-kharif rice crops are increasing.

Two species of the pentatomid bug were identified by the Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta, as *Dolycoris indicus* Stal and *D. baccarum* Linn (see figure). Nymphs and adults damage rice by sucking plant sap and milk from panicles in dough stage. Panicle sterility averaged 10%. Populations were highest in Apr, when it was not unusual to find 2–3 insects per plant.¹

Rice hispa in Burdwan, West Bengal

D.K. Banerjee and D.K. Nath, Entomology Section, Government of West Bengal, Adaptive Crop Production Research Station, Kalna Road, Burdwan, West Bengal, India

Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* occurs

in only a few areas of West Bengal. In 1984 kharif there was a severe hispa outbreak on 62,341 ha of rice in 5 southern districts.

Data from Burdwan District, which had 24,575 ha attacked by hispa, showed 4 broods during 1984 kharif. The first developed just after